

Synthesis and photoelectrochemical studies on lithium titanium(IV) molybdate

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Lithium titanium(IV) molybdate was prepared by the solid-state reaction between the corresponding oxides. It crystallizes in tetragonal symmetry with lattice parameters, $a_0 = 14.709 \text{ \AA}$ and $c_0 = 21.134 \text{ \AA}$. Band gap of the compound was found to be 1.33 eV from electrical conductivity study. Photoelectrochemical (PEC) cell parameter like flat band potential was located at -0.44 V . Solar to electrical conversion efficiency (η) was found to be 0.14%.

As a part of our programme to evaluate the oxide semiconductor materials^{1,2} for their photoelectrochemical (PEC) behavior lithium titanium(IV) molybdate have been explored. Plane titanium(IV) molybdate reported earlier showed poor solar to electrical conversion efficiency but remarkable stability when used as photoanode in photoelectrochemical cell. Lithium mixed metal molybdate reported earlier showed improved solar to electrical conversion efficiency. The paper reports synthesis of lithium titanium(IV) molybdate and its application as photoelectrode in PEC cell.

Results and discussion

Chemical analysis and X-ray diffraction :

Chemical analysis and XRD powder pattern of the compound $\text{Li}_2\text{TiO}(\text{MoO}_4)_2$ confirm the formation of single crystalline phase. From the chemical analysis it was observed that there was a good agreement between theoretical and experimental values for Li, Ti and Mo content.

The formation of crystalline single phase of the compound was checked by comparing experimental XRD data (Table 1) with the corresponding data for reacting oxides and probable alteration products available in JCPDS data file. It is observed that only a single phase has been formed and the XRD pattern neither contains the reflections due to reacting oxides nor their alteration product. The XRD pattern (Fig. 1) of the compound was indexed using standard indexing procedure³. It crystallizes in tetragonal symmetry with lattice parameters, $a_0 = 14.709$ and $c_0 = 21.134 \text{ \AA}$.

Electrical conductivity :

Temperature-dependence of the electrical conductivity

Table 1. Results of XRD study of $\text{Li}_2\text{TiO}(\text{MoO}_4)_2$

hkl	d_{obs}	d_{cal}	hkl
13.80	5.283	5.283	004
13.97	4.532	4.543	311
23.51	4.420	4.446	302
51.62	3.409	3.421	331
100.00	3.375	3.380	412
32.03	3.324	3.334	116
40.03	3.262	3.260	403
13.29	3.031	3.019	007
18.57	2.584	2.581	441
20.95	2.498	2.505	531
13.80	2.192	2.193	630
19.42	1.692	1.694	736
14.65	1.688	1.688	752

Fig. 1. XRD pattern of $\text{Li}_2\text{TiO}(\text{MoO}_4)_2$.

is shown in Fig. 2. The plot of $\log \sigma$ vs $1/T$ indicates the semiconducting nature and consists of two straight-line portions having different slopes. Low temperature electrical

Fig. 2. Temperature dependence of the electrical conductivity of $\text{Li}_2\text{TiO}(\text{MoO}_4)_2$.

conductivity is due to extrinsic conduction, which is due to the presence of impurities, moisture, etc., whereas the conduction in the higher temperature range is intrinsic type. Activation energy of conduction for low and high temperature regions and temperature of change of slope for $\text{Li}_2\text{TiO}(\text{MoO}_4)_2$ has values of 0.49 eV, 0.67 eV and 500 K, respectively. The electrical band gap from intrinsic conduction has a value of 1.33 eV. Electrical conductivity in solids can be explained on the basis of band theory. The hopping of charge carriers in the narrow $3d$ -band dominates at lower temperatures whereas band like conduction in $\text{O}^{2-} : 2\text{P}$ band is predominant in the higher temperature region and is able to suppress the conduction due to hopping⁵. The change in the conduction mechanism is indicated by the change in slope of $\log \sigma$ vs $1/T$ plot and depends upon the hopping energy involved, structural imperfections and impurity states.

Thermoelectric power :

The variation of thermoelectric power as a function of temperature is found to be negative over the entire range of temperature studied and hence the compound is an n -type semiconductor and the majority charge carriers are electrons.

Photoelectrochemical (PEC) studies :

The pellets of lithium mixed molybdate of titanium(IV) showed high resistivity ($10^8 \Omega \text{ cm}$) at room temperature. In order to obtain maximum photoresponse, the semiconductor electrode should have low resistivity⁶. Therefore, before utilizing the pellet of $\text{Li}_2\text{TiO}(\text{MoO}_4)_2$ as a photoanode in the PEC cell, its resistivity was lowered down to minimum practical value by sintering the pellet in a hydrogen atmosphere⁷. The lowering of resistivity is interpreted in terms of oxygen deficiency, which in turn enhances electrical conductivity. The resistivity was brought down to nearly $10^2 \Omega \text{ cm}$.

From the point of view of energy conversion it would be desirable to select redox couple whose redox potential is situated within the band gap of a semiconductor and ideally should lie close to E_{vb} for n -type semiconductor and E_{cb} for p -type semiconductor⁸. From the values of E_c (-6.340 eV) and E_v (-7.670 eV), $\text{Fe}^{3+}/\text{Fe}^{2+}$ redox couple seems to be a better choice as a common electrolyte for fabrication of PEC cell. The optimum pH for this redox electrolyte system was found to be 2 and it was observed that the photoanode did not get corroded or damaged under these conditions. Thus the PEC cell with following configuration was constructed :

The measurements of space charge layer capacitance with respect to applied potential have been carried out at 1 kHz. Assuming that the major contribution of the capacitance arises from space-charge layer, the data were treated by Mott-Schottky relation. A linear curve between $1/C^2$ and applied potential gave on extrapolation, the value of flat band potential (V_{fb}) as -0.44 eV vs SCE. The capacitance-voltage study also indicates n -type nature of the electrode. The maximum power efficiency and the fill factor were calculated from the current-voltage (I - V) characteristics of the PEC cell. The photocurrent and photovoltage of the semiconductor electrode were measured at different biased potentials. The close circuit current (I_{sc}) and open-circuit voltage (V_{oc}) of the PEC cell were found to be 0.18 mA and 0.24 V, respectively. The maximum current (I_{max}) and maximum voltage (V_{max}) for the cell came out to be 0.113 mA and 0.125 V, respectively. Hence the fill factor and power efficiency were calculated to be 0.319 and 0.14%, respectively. The low power efficiency may be attributed to high internal resistance of cell, polarization, and surface recombination centers on the electrode surface⁹.

Conclusion :

The present investigation shows that the power conversion efficiency of lithium mixed molybdate of titanium(IV) is low but in comparison with simple titanium(IV) molybdates studied earlier¹ the power conversion efficiency is found to be higher. Attempts are being made to increase the conversion efficiency of $\text{Li}_2\text{TiO}(\text{MoO}_4)_2$ by using it in the form of thin film or single crystal as a photoanode in place of polycrystalline material.

Experimental

All chemicals used were of A.R. grade. $\text{Li}_2\text{TiO}(\text{MoO}_4)_2$ was prepared by method of solid-state reaction of corresponding oxides. Stoichiometric amounts of Li_2CO_3 , TiO_2 and MoO_3 were thoroughly mixed and ground in an agate motor using high purity acetone for homogeneity. To this finely ground powder 5% solution of polyvinyl acetate in acetone (as a binder) was added¹⁰. About 2 ml solution per gram of powder was found to be fairly satisfactory for the purpose. The powder mixture was pressed to pellets (1.2 cm dia). The pellets were first slowly heated up to 300° for ~3 h to evaporate the binder and finally fired in air at 650° for 30 h in an electric furnace. They were then furnace-cooled at the rate of 1°/min.

The chemical composition of lithium titanium(IV) molybdate was determined by estimating its metal contents¹¹. Its formation was further confirmed by X-ray diffraction (XRD) using a Philips PW 1700 diffractometer with $\text{CuK}\alpha$ radiation. Direct current (DC) resistivity of lithium titanium(IV) molybdate was measured as a function of temperature up to 800 K by standard two-probe method using BPL-India RM 160 MK IIIA Million Mega-Ohmmeter. A good ohmic contact was made by applying a thin layer of silver paste to both the surfaces of a pellet with subsequent drying at 300° for 1 h. The thermoelectric power was measured with a Philips PM 2522/90 multimeter with accuracy better than $\pm 0.20\%$. A temperature difference (ΔT) of 20° was produced across the pellet with the help of a micro-furnace fitted with the sample holder assembly and temperature of both the surfaces of the pellet were recorded by chromel-alumel thermocouple attached to the platinum electrode. Each reading was taken after attaining thermal equilibrium (~2.5 h). In all the measurements, the two-electrode method was employed and mica sheets were used for insulation.

The pellets of $\text{Li}_2\text{TiO}(\text{MoO}_4)_2$ was sintered in hydrogen atmosphere at 500° for 2 h to reduce the high value of room temperature resistivity to $10^2 \Omega \text{ cm}$. A further decrease in

resistivity could not be achieved as only mild hydrogen sintering conditions had to be used to avoid reduction. The electrode for PEC measurements was prepared using these sintered pellets. Silver paste was applied on one of the surfaces of the pellet and ohmic contact between the supporting copper wire and silver coated surface was made. This surface was then covered with epoxy. The counter electrode was made by spot-welding a platinum wire to a 1-cm² platinum plate. The PEC cell arrangement and subsequent measurements were made using the procedures described elsewhere⁸.

A single compartment cell contained a semiconducting electrode of $\text{Li}_2\text{TiO}(\text{MoO}_4)_2$ and a counter electrode with 0.1 M $\text{Fe}^{2+}/\text{Fe}^{3+}$ redox couple was prepared from solutions of ferrous ammonium sulfate and ferric ammonium sulfate as follows :

The pH of the electrolyte was adjusted to 0.5, 1.0, 1.5, 2.0 and 2.5, and photoresponse was measured. All potentials are referred to SCE. The light source used was a 150 W tungsten-halogen lamp. Light was passed through an optically flat pyrex window. Polychromatic light intensity was measured by using a standard silicon cell (Suryamapi supplied by Central Electronic Ltd.). The PEC cell properties such as capacitance-voltage and photocurrent-photovoltage were measured to determine the parameters, flat-band potential (V_{fb}), fill factor and power conversion efficiency.

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